

HARMONIZATION OF GLOBAL AND LOCAL CULTURES

Asrakulova Adiba Nabievna

Teacher of Namangan state pedagogical institute
Doctor of philosophy (PhD) philosophical sciences
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18546310>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07th February 2026

Accepted: 08th February 2026

Online: 09th February 2026

KEYWORDS

globalization, national identity, identity, culture, society, socio-philosophical analysis

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the concept of national identity and its socio-philosophical essence in society in the process of globalization. The issues of preserving national identity, the formation of identity and its harmonization with global cultural processes are covered from a scientific perspective. Modern problems and philosophical ways to solve them are also considered.

Introduction. There are also conflicting opinions and approaches about the impact of globalization on culture, education, morality, heritage, spiritual wealth, the consciousness and imagination of young people. The impact of globalization on socio-political and economic life cannot be logically and objectively reflected in subjective factors.

Therefore, the impact of globalization on culture and spirituality must be objectively revealed. Unfortunately, our experts, especially social scientists and spiritualists, seek to find some negative effects from globalization, try not to see its positive aspects, and even if they do, do not express an opinion. As a result, globalization is limited to “mass culture” and “spiritual threats”. Globalization, as in socio-economic and international integration, is manifested as a reality, a phenomenon with both positive and negative aspects in the field of culture and spirituality.

The process of globalization is one of the most important socio-territorial phenomena of the 21st century, which is fundamentally changing human life by uniting the political, economic, cultural and information spheres.[1] At the same time, globalization processes are also strengthening the need to preserve national identity, cultural heritage and traditional values.[2] The concept of national identity is a set of unique cultural, historical, linguistic, and spiritual characteristics of a people or nation that determine the identity of an individual and society.[3]

Globalization and its socio-philosophical impact. A philosophical analysis of globalization shows that this process includes not only economic and political integration, but also the global interaction of cultural and moral values.[4] Robertson notes that the globalization process “creates an integral whole in local and global interaction, which requires the adaptation of national cultures and traditions to a new context.” Giddens defines globalization as “a process that changes the social structures of society, leading to the formation of new identities and spiritual values in interpersonal and interstate relations”.

The concept of national identity and its significance National identity is a complex of cultural and historical aspects that allow an individual and society to distinguish themselves from others.[5] It includes language, tradition, historical experience, religious and spiritual values. From a philosophical point of view, national identity is the basis of the social identity of an individual.[6]

The interaction of national identity and global processes. In the process of globalization, national identity develops in two directions: Testing and Renewal and harmonization. For example, in the process of post-independence development of Uzbekistan, the preservation and modernization of national identity was identified as an important strategic direction.[7]

Contemporary problems and solutions In the context of modern globalization, national identity faces the following problems: The risk of losing the national language and traditions; The weakening of cultural identity among young people; The neglect of local values in the global information flow. To overcome this, philosophical and practical approaches are necessary. Today, innovations and creative products created and discovered in Uzbekistan will soon spread to other continents and the world. Other peoples will benefit from them. The expansion of intercultural contacts and integration serves the formation of a universal society and universal unity. No factor can unite peoples, nations and states as widely and deeply as culture, and the artifacts and wealth embedded in their socio-cultural existence become a global reality. Being universal is in the essence of national cultures, and even when they serve a specific local ethnic group or group of people, they retain their universal basis.

Conclusion. The process of globalization creates new challenges and opportunities for national identity. It is important for preserving and developing national identity, ensuring social stability and cultural harmony.

References:

1. Robertson, R. (1992). *Globalization: Social Theory and Global Culture*. London: Sage.
2. Giddens, A. (1990). *The Consequences of Modernity*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
3. Smith, A. D. (1991). *National Identity*. Reno: University of Nevada Press.
4. Taylor, C. (1994). *Multiculturalism: Examining the Politics of Recognition*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
5. Held, D. (1999). *Global Transformations*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
6. Castells, M. (1997). *The Power of Identity*. Oxford: Blackwell.
7. Mirziyoev, Sh. M. (2019). *Development concept of Uzbekistan until 2030*. Tashkent.